

The Influence of the Cooperative Script Method on the German Reading Ability of Class XI IPS Student at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to see the effect of the Cooperative Script method on the German reading ability of class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar. The research method used is quantitative with Pre-experimental research type and One Group Pretest-Posttest research design. The research population was class XI IPS of SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar as many as 167 people. Based on the results of data analysis and the hypotheses tested, it is known that there is an increase in the ability to read German texts in class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar by applying the Cooperative Script method. This is proven by the results of the normality test analysis with a pretest score of 0.051 ($0.05 < 0.051$) and a posttest score of 0.069 ($0.05 < 0.069$). Then, based on the statistical hypothesis test using the paired samples test, a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$ was produced, meaning that the calculated statistical results (t output number) $<$ table statistics (t -table), it was concluded that H_0 was rejected and H_1 was accepted. Thus, the Cooperative Script method has the effect of increasing the ability to read German texts in class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar.

INTRODUCTION

German is a foreign language that is categorized as international communication. German has also been studied at school at high school level. There are 4 German language skills namely; Hoerverstehen listening skills , Sprechfertigkeit speaking skills , Leseverstehen reading skills , Schreibfertigkeit writing skills . These four language skills must be mastered by students so that they can support students' reading abilities. Reading is an important skill in learning German. Reading skills can be done by listening to the teacher's explanation of how the reading instructions are carried out. However, in this study the researchers only focused on one skill, namely Leseverstehen reading skills. German is currently being studied in high schools, including at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar as a specialization subject. The curriculum currently used at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar is the 2013 Curriculum (K-13). According to Mulyasa (2013: 66), the 2013 curriculum is a competency-based curriculum with a curriculum concept that emphasizes character development and task competence in accordance with certain achievement standards.

Based on the core competencies listed in the 2013 curriculum in class using methods according to scientific principles. Especially in reading skills, students are expected to be able to observe and pay attention to the form of text, and write words, phrases or sentences in written discourse.

Based on the researcher's observations during PPL at SMA Negeri 5 Pematangsiantar, namely, students' lack of interest in learning German, students' lack of self-confidence when reading German texts, students are not used to reading German texts, the way of learning still uses lecture/conventional methods. so students tend to feel bored.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The Nature of Learning German as a Foreign Language

Learning is an interaction process carried out to gain knowledge and new knowledge between teachers and students. Language is a means of verbal communication that has symbols and sounds produced from someone's speech.

Chaer, et al (2007: 32) put forward a definition of language, namely that language is a system of arbitrary sound symbols used by members of a social group to work together, communicate and identify themselves. Wiratno, et al (2014: 4) expressed the opinion that language has three basic functions, namely expression function, information function and exploration-function. The function of expression is language that expresses feelings of happiness or sadness, admiration and so on. The information function is something that is used to convey messages to other people. The exploration function is the language used to explain a case and a situation.

According to Ghazali (2000: 11) that foreign language learning is a process of learning a language that cannot be used as communication material in one's environment, but is only studied at school and cannot be used for daily communication in society, for example German, English, French, and Arabic. It can be concluded that the foreign language studied is an introductory language to improve a person's language skills with the aim of being a means of

communication in accordance with its function. Language skills relate to abilities related to the use of language in real communication in everyday life.

The Nature of German Reading Ability

Wahyuni and Ibrahim (2012: 27) state that reading is a process that includes both physical and psychological processes. Nurgiyantoro (1988: 225-226) stated that reading is an activity related to mental speech expressed by other parties through written means to understand the spoken language being read. Therefore, in reading activities, you have to recognize certain written symbols which contain certain meanings.

In general, reading can be said to be a psycholinguistic process where the reader reconstructs messages encoded by the writer in the form of graphic symbols (Goodman, 1973:22). In line with this, Tarigan (1984:7) believes that reading can be understood as a process carried out and used by readers to obtain messages conveyed by writers through written media. From these two opinions it can be concluded that reading is a process of reconstructing graphic symbols that have been encoded in order to obtain messages or information conveyed by the author through written media.

The Nature of Measuring Reading Ability

The essence of reading is a very important skill for individuals to master. Saleh Abbas (2006: 101) expressed his opinion that reading is essentially an activity carried out to obtain reading information both explicitly and implicitly in the form of evaluative and creative understanding by utilizing the reader's experience that has been carried out. This was also mentioned by Farida Rahim (2005: 1) who stated that in reading activities there are three terms that are often used to provide basic components in the reading process, including recording, decoding and meaning.

Based on the opinions above, it can be concluded that the nature of reading is a complicated process and requires carefulness when pronouncing the sentences that are read which are physical and psychological in nature, the process in the form of physical activities that observe the writing correctly, and the psychological process of observing the writing to the center of consciousness through human nerves.

The Nature of Cooperative Learning Methods (Cooperative Learning)

Cooperative Script method is a student learning method that directs students to work together in pairs to achieve learning goals. In the ongoing learning process, reading has become a basic activity that students can do to find out something they did not know before.

Cooperative Script learning, there is an agreement between students regarding the rules for using this method, that is, students agree with each other to carry out their respective roles. In using the Cooperative Script method there are two roles, namely the first role as reader and the second role as listener. Students who act as readers will read the learning questions given by the teacher and students who act as listeners will listen to what the reader reads

and will remind the reader if there are errors. The benefit of the cooperative script method is to train students in the accuracy and accuracy of cooperation by all groups in learning discussions.

Based on the opinion expressed above, it can be concluded that the Cooperative Script method is a cooperative learning method which aims to increase students' understanding of the subject matter provided by the teacher by discussing it with their friends. This Cooperative Script method will make students play a more active role and help each other in learning to read German.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

METHODOLOGY

In this research, the research design used was One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design . The pretest is before the teaching treatment is given and the posttest is after the teaching treatment is given. In one class the experiment was carried out twice before and after treatment. Pretest (O 1), namely before carrying out treatment , and posttest (O 2) namely after treatment. The results of the Pretest and Posttest treatment can be seen how the Cooperative Script learning method influences the reading ability of class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar. This research design can be described as follows.

Table 1. Pre-Test and Post-Test Research Design

<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Treatment</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>
O ₁	X	O ₂

Information :

- O₁ = Pretest (initial test score) reading ability before use Cooperative Script method.
- X = Treatment (Treatment) Using Cooperative learning methods Scripts.
- O₂ = Posttest (final test score) reading ability after use Cooperative Script learning method .

RESULTS

The aim of this research was to determine the effect of the Cooperative Script Method on the German Reading Ability of Class XI IPS Students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar. In this research experimental class, there were 32 students. Then work on Pretest and Posttest questions , with the One Group Pretest-Posttest Design type . In the experimental class, it was carried out twice, namely before and after treatment without a control class. Research in the experimental class, namely class.

1. Pretest Score Data

The following is the average Pretest score (before applying the Cooperative Script learning method).

$$M = \frac{\sum X}{\sum Y}$$

$$M = \frac{1320}{32}$$

$$M = 41.25$$

From the results of the average student score before applying the Cooperative Script learning method, the score was below the KKM (still low score).

Table 2. Pretest Descriptive Statistical Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics		
Pre Test		
N	Valid	32
	Missing	0
Mean		41.25
Median		40.00
Mode		40
Std. Deviation		10.000
Variance		100.000
Minimum		20

Maximum	70
Sum	1320

Sumber : IBM SPSS 29 for Windows

The table above can be explained that the average (Mean) Pretest value is 41.25. With a total of 32 students. With the lowest value (Minimum) being 20 and the highest value (Maximum) 70, the middle value (Median) amounting to 40.00, the variance value is 100,000, the standard deviation (Std. Deviation) is 10,000, the mode value is 40, and the total number of numbers in the data (Sum) is 1320. So it can be concluded from the results of the average value. On average, there was no increase in the scores of class XI IPS students regarding their reading ability in the pre-test. So there must be a Cooperative Script learning method for the German reading ability of class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar so that students' grades can increase.

2. Posttest Score Data

The following is the average Posttest score (after applying the Cooperative Script learning method).

$$M = \frac{\sum X}{\sum Y}$$

$$M = \frac{2865}{32}$$

$$M = 89.53$$

From the results of the average student scores after applying the Cooperative Script learning method, the scores were above the KKM (increased scores).

Table 3. Posttest Descriptive Statistical Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics		
Post Test		
N	Valid	32
	Missing	0
Mean		89.53
Median		90.00
Mode		90
Std. Deviation		6.643
Variance		44.128
Minimum		75
Maximum		100
Sum		2865

Sumber : IBM SPSS 29 for Windows

The table above can be explained that the average (Mean) Posttest score is 89.53 , and the number of students is 32 people, with the lowest score

(Minimum) 75 and the highest value (Maximum) 100, the middle value (Median) 90.00, the variance value (Variance) 44,128, the standard deviation (Std. Deviation) 6,643, for the mode value (Mode) 90. and the total number of numbers in the data (Sum) which is 2865. So it can be concluded from the results of the average posttest score that there is an increase in class XI IPS students' reading ability scores. So there is an influence of the Cooperative Script learning method on the German reading ability of class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar.

Data Normality Test Results

Data is said to be normal if the significant value is greater than 0.05 at ($P > 0.05$). Conversely, if the significant value is smaller than 0.05 at ($P < 0.05$) then the data is said to be abnormal. This Normality Test was carried out to see the normality of the pre-test and post-test score data for Class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar.

Table 4. Data Normality Test Table
 Tests of Normality

	Shapiro-Wilk Statistics	df	Sig.
Pretest	,934	32	,051
Posttest	,939	32	,069

Source: IBM SPSS 29 for Windows

The table above can be explained that the significance value (Sig.) for the pre-test is .051, for the statistical value (Statistics) it is 0.934, and the degree of freedom (df) is 32. Then the significance value (Sig.) for the post-test is 0.069, for the statistical value (Statistics) amounted to 0.939, and the degree of freedom (df) was 32, so it was concluded that the significance value (Sig.) of the pre-test score was 0.051 ($0.05 < 0.051$) and the post-test score was 0.069 ($0.05 < 0.069$). So based on the Shapiro-Wilk test, the data is declared to be normally distributed. After the normality test is carried out and the data is declared normal, the next hypothesis test will be carried out. Hypothesis testing is a statistical science that is used to test the truth of data whether to accept or reject a hypothesis. Hypothesis testing was carried out to determine whether there was a significant influence between the results before and after the Cooperative Script method was carried out on the German reading ability of class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar. The hypothesis test used in this research is the paired sample t-test. This test is used with paired samples, namely the same sample but experiencing different treatment, namely with a pre-test and posttest. So it can be concluded whether there is an influence of the Cooperative Script method on the German reading ability of class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar. The hypothesis of this research is as follows:

1. H0 : There is no influence of the Cooperative Script method on the German reading ability of class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar.
2. H1 : There is an influence of the Cooperative Script method on the German reading ability of class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar.

The results are presented as follows:

Table 5. T-Test Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Significance	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				One-Sided p	Two-Sided p
				Lower	Upper				
Pre Test - Post Test	-48,281	6,551	1,158	-50,643	-45,919	-41,690	31	<.001	<.001

Source: IBM SPSS 29 For Windows

A study is said to have a proven hypothesis if the sig value. Less than 0.05 (sig. < 0.05), then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted.

The table above explains that the average value (Mean) on the pre-test and post-test is -48.281, the standard deviation (Std. Deviation) value of the pre-test and post-test is 6.551, the average standard error value (Std. Error Mean) pre-test and post-test is 1.158, (95% Confidence Interval for Mean) the lowest pre-test and post-test score (Lower Bound) is -50.643 , and the highest pre-test and post-test score (Upper Bound) is -45.919 . The pre-test and post-test t (test) values are -41.690 with degrees of freedom (df) amounting to 31. The pre-test and post-test significance values are 0.001, so it can be concluded that it is smaller than 0.05, which means there is a significant influence that is if the Sig value. (2-sided p) < 0.05, then Ho is rejected and H₁ is accepted. This shows that there is quite a big influence on the German reading ability of class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar by applying the Cooperative Script method.

DISCUSSION

Cooperative Script Learning Method on the German reading ability of Class XI IPS Students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar. The type of research carried out was Pre Experimental with One Group Pre-test and Post-test Design. The population in this study was the entire class XI IPS of SMA Negeri

5 Pematang Siantar with a sample of one experimental class chosen at random, namely class

In the research implementation stage, the researcher gives an initial test (pre-test) to measure students' reading abilities before being given treatment, then the researcher will teach how to learn using the Cooperative Script method. Next, they will give a final test (post-test) to measure students' reading abilities after being given treatment.

After the research stage was completed, the researcher analyzed the data on the Pretest and Posttest results. Pretest average score results is 41.25. With the highest value being 70 and the lowest value being 20. Meanwhile, the average Post-test score is 89.53 with the highest score being 100 and the lowest score being 75. From the results of these average scores it can be concluded that the Post-test average score is higher than the Pre-test average score .

Then, after the average value of the Pre-test and Post-test is known, a normality test will be carried out using Shapiro-Wilk. The normality test is carried out to determine whether the research data obtained is normally distributed or vice versa. The resulting sig value. (significant) pretest in this study was 0.051 ($0.05 < 0.051$) and the sig. (significant) posttest in this study was 0.069 ($0.05 < 0.069$). So it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

Paired Sample T-test will be carried out . The Paired Sample T-test in this study obtained a significant value of 0.001, which means that there is a significant influence that can be concluded to be smaller than 0.005, so H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. Thus, the Cooperative Script method influences the German reading ability of class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the data analysis that has been completed, the researcher put forward the following conclusions:

1. Score for students' reading ability before treatment (Pretest) was 41.25 and the average score (Posttest) after treatment was applied namely 89.53. So it can be concluded that the average posttest score is higher than the pretest score, which means that the Cooperative Script method influences the reading ability of class XI IPS students at SMA Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar.
2. This is proven by the data normality test using Shapiro-Wilk where the Pretest significance value is 0.051 and the Posttest significance value is 0.069. So it can be concluded that the value (sig.) is greater than 0.05, which means the research data is normal.
3. Then, from the results of the Paired Sample T-test that has been carried out, the significance value obtained is $0.001 < 0.05$, which means there is a significant influence, so that H_1 in this study is accepted and declared successful and the H_0 hypothesis is rejected.

Based on the conclusions stated above, there are several suggestions as follows:

1. Advice for Teachers

It is hoped that teachers can apply the Cooperative Script method to German reading skills so that students have an interest in learning German.

2. Advice for Students

It is hoped that with the Cooperative Script learning method students can improve their reading skills when learning German, and students will play an active role while learning is taking place.

3. Suggestions for Researchers

It is hoped that future researchers will be able to develop more deeply the influence of the Cooperative Script method on German reading ability.

FURTHER STUDY

Every research is subject to limitations; thus, you can explain them here and briefly provide suggestions to further investigations.

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